

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PROJECT BASED LEARNING TO IMPROVE B2 LEVEL STUDENTS’ SPEAKING SKILL

Turgunboeva Dilnoza Akmal qizi

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages, Faculty of English Philology, Teacher of the
Department of English Functional Lexicon

d.turgunboeva@uzswlu.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814891>

Abstract. Speaking considered as the result of studying English or it is the main goal of language learning, it represents all the other aspects of language skills which means that having a good speaking most likely having a good knowledge because through speaking, people can share their ideas, get and produce information and the speaker should be able to choose the lexicon, grammatical structures, the choice of words and topics so that the utterances which are said by the speaker can be understood by the listener. Therefore, students of philological higher education institutions need to develop oral speech skills in order to be able to freely communicate in English, exchange ideas. In this graduation work, an effective method of teaching students to develop speaking skill is recommended.

Keywords: communication, authentic materials, discourse, critical thinking, integration of skills, problem solving, evaluation, feedback, formative assessment, content.

Аннотация. Разговорная речь, рассматриваемая как результат изучения английского языка или являющаяся основной целью изучения языка, представляет собой все остальные аспекты языковых навыков, что означает, что хорошая разговорная речь, скорее всего, обладает хорошими знаниями, потому что посредством разговорной речи люди могут делиться своими идеями, получать и продуцировать информацию, и говорящий должен уметь подбирать лексику, грамматические структуры, подбирать слова и темы таким образом, чтобы высказывания, произносимые говорящим, были понятны слушателю. Поэтому студентам филологических вузов необходимо развивать навыки устной речи, чтобы иметь возможность свободно общаться на английском языке, обмениваться идеями. В данной дипломной работе рекомендуется эффективный метод обучения студентов развитию разговорных навыков.

Ключевые слова: коммуникация, аутентичные материалы, дискурс, критическое мышление, интеграция навыков, решение проблем, оценка, обратная связь, формирующая оценка, содержание.

Annotatsiya. Til o‘rganishda asosiy maqsadlardan biri og‘zaki nutqni shakllantirish, shu tilda erkin muloqot qila olish, chunki mukammal og‘zaki nutq mukammal bilim darajasini ifodalaydi. Og‘zaki nutq kishilarga fikr almashishga, ma‘lumotlarni qabul qilish va uzatishga imkon beradi va bunda tinglovchiga tushunarli bo‘lishi uchun so‘zlovchidan mavzuga aloqador kerakli so‘zlarni tanlay olish, to‘g‘ri grammatik strukturani qo‘llash talab etiladi. Shu sababli filologik oliy ta‘lim muassasalari talabalari ingliz tilida erkin muloqot qila olish, fikr almashish uchun og‘zaki nutq ko‘nikmalarini rivojlanitirishi kerak. Mazkur bitiruv ishida talabalarni og‘zaki nutq mahoratini rivojlanitirish uchun samarali o‘qitish usuli tavsiya etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: muloqot, autentik materiallar, nutq, tanqidiy fikrlash, ko‘nikmalarni birlashtirish, muammolarni hal qilish, baholash, izoh, shakllantiruvchi baholash, tarkib.

Project work encourages students to use language intentionally because it demands personal engagement from the start. Students must decide what they will do and how they will do

it, including the language requirements as well as the project's content, in consultation with their instructor.

1. A greater sense of motivation as students take an active role in the project.
2. Reading, writing, speaking, and listening are the four integrated skills.
3. The promotion of autonomous learning occurs as students assume greater responsibility for their own learning.
4. There are learning results -learners have an end product.
5. Authentic tasks and therefore the language input are more authentic.
6. Interpersonal relations are developed through working as a team.
7. Content and methodology can be decided between the learners and the teacher and within the group, themselves so it is more learner centered.
8. Learners often get help from parents for project work thus involving the parent more in the child's learning. If the project is also displayed parents can see it at open days or when they pick the child up from the school.
9. A break from routine and the chance to do something different.
10. A context is established which balances the need for fluency and accuracy. There is no one right way to use projects in your class. The most difficult stage is selection of a project type according to teacher's goal, curriculum requirements, students' need and level etc. There are several key features of a good project and some of the most essential criteria for project selection can be the following.

The first criterion for selection is making decision what type of project students will benefit most. Projects can be divided into several different categories, all of which can be used to enrich the curriculum, strengthen Internet skills, and provide integrated and thematic learning opportunities. Each type of project can be structured as individual student projects, in-class collaborative learning groups, or class-to-class interactions. In project-based learning, teachers play the role of facilitators. Instead of giving up authority over the classroom or the education of the students, they foster a culture of shared accountability. The suggested topic or problem must be organized by the teacher in a way that focuses the students' learning on content-based information. To guarantee that student projects stay on target and that students have a thorough comprehension of the ideas being studied, they must control student achievement using sporadic, transitional goals. Through continuous evaluations and feedback, the students are held responsible for meeting these objectives. To make sure the student stays within the parameters of the main issue and the fundamental principles the project is attempting to explore, continuous evaluation and feedback are crucial.

In order to be transparent to both adults and children, formative assessments are employed, according to Andrew Miller of the Buck Institute of Education. “You need to be able to track and monitor ongoing formative assessments, that show work toward that standard.” These tests are used by the instructor to direct the students' inquiry and make sure they have learnt the necessary material. After the project is completed, the teacher assesses the knowledge that it has demonstrated and the final result. PBL makes students assume responsibility for their own achievement. Students who participate in developing the project assignment or project checklist also get invaluable experience in establishing their own objectives and benchmarks for excellence. Students feel more in charge of and in control of their own learning as a result. Students also get the chance to find relevant subtopics and investigate them in a project-based setting. Students can

collaborate with classmates and mentors in a student-centered setting where they are encouraged to explore a variety of interests while teaching with the project-based method.

REFERENCES

1. Bell, S. (2010). Project-based learning for the 21st century: Skills for the future. *ClearingHouse*, 83(2), 39-43.
2. Cheung, S. M. & Chow, A. T. (2011) 'Project-based learning: a student investigation of the turtle trade in Guangzhou, People's Republic of China'. *Journal of Biological Education*, 45 (2). pp 68-76.
3. Donnelly, R. & Fitzmaurice, M. (2005) 'Collaborative project-based learning and problem-based learning in higher education: A consideration of tutor and student roles in learner-focused strategies'. *Emerging Issues in the Practice of University Learning and Teaching*. Dublin: AISHE, pp 87-98.